

№ 36.
E-mail: teymurz@yandex.ru

Features of Features of Securing the Ownership of Digitalized Objects of Civil Rights

T. E. Zulfugarzade

PhD of Law, Associate Professor, Associate Professor of the Department
of Civil Legal Disciplines of the PRUE.
Address: Plekhanov Russian University of Economics, 36 Stremyanny Lane,
Moscow, 117997, Russian Federation.
E-mail: teymurz@yandex.ru

Abstract

The article defines the main directions in the field of blockchain-securing the ownership of digitalized (digital) objects of Civil Law, primarily for non-fiat cryptocurrencies and tokens (digital tokens), as well as other assets, for example, user accounts in electronic payment systems, popular online electronic games, social networks and others, existing exclusively in digital form, the cost of which can be very significant. The research methodology is based on the definition of innovative approaches in notarial activities; the analysis of Romano-Germanic and Anglo-Saxon legal systems, in their adaptation to decentralization; on the definition and concretization of the legal and technical-technological features of the decentralized blockchain-consolidate the identity of Civil Law objects from the point of view of their fault tolerance, attack resistance and collusion resistance. The scientific novelty of the research is determined by the author's proposals aimed at improving the legal support of the legal mechanism of the blockchain-securing the ownership of digital objects that are important for the protection of the citizens and organizations interests, including in the implementation of commercial and other economic activities, as well as digital rights passing in the order of inheritance (succession); further possibility of using blockchain-secured digital rights as evidence in Civil and Arbitration processes.

1. « ». 2017. 5 . - URL: [https://zakon.rU/blog/2017/6/5/yuridicheskie _aspekty_ primneniya_blokchejna_i_ispolzovaniya_kriptoaktivov](https://zakon.rU/blog/2017/6/5/yuridicheskie_aspekty_primneniya_blokchejna_i_ispolzovaniya_kriptoaktivov) (: 05.03.2019).
2. // (LAN). - 2017. - 12. - . 20-22.
3. . 2017. 16 - URL: [https://utmagazine. ru/posts/21332-osobennosti-tehnologii-blokcheyn](https://utmagazine.ru/posts/21332-osobennosti-tehnologii-blokcheyn) (: 05.03.2019).
4. Benet J. Design Challenge: Avoid Centralization and Singletons, 2017. - URL: [http://scuttlebot.io/more/ articles/design-challenge-avoid-centralization-and-singletons.html](http://scuttlebot.io/more/articles/design-challenge-avoid-centralization-and-singletons.html) (: 05.03.2019).
5. Blockchain Technology: Implications for the Legal Industry Boston. The American Lawyer, 2018. November, 30. - P. 1-4.
6. Buterin V. D. The Meaning of 2017. February, 6. - URL: <https://medium.com/@VitalikButerin/the-meaning-of-decentralization-a0c92b76a274> (: 05.03.2019).
7. Civalleri J. When «Code is Law meets» «Law is Law» - Inside the American Bar Association's Biggest Blockchain Event of the Year. A Medium Corporation. 2017. April, 13. - URL: <https://hackernoon.com/when-code-is-law-meets-law-is-law-inside-the-american-bar-associations-biggest-blockchain-c76e3bafbb9a> (: 05.03.2019).
8. Ferguson N. Civilization: The West and the Rest. - London : Penguin Group. 2012. - P. 1042.